

D6.2

Guidance document for Pilots on collaborative systems analysis approaches

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D6.2/Guidance document for Pilots on collaborative systems analysis approaches

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Abstract

Collaborative systems analysis approaches are needed for forward-looking adaptive multi-risk decision making for a variety of reasons, including (i) to avoid negative consequences when approaching problems through a sector-specific lens, (ii) to aid in the formulation of system-wide objectives that both recognize and balance the inherent trade-offs within our systems, (iii) to ensure a more equitable distribution of system-wide resources, costs and benefits, and (iv) to help reduce the potential for stakeholder conflict. In this light, the principal purpose of collaborative systems analysis approaches is to help describe decision-making contexts in all their complexity.

This brief report presents the findings of a literature review on promising tools and approaches for collaborative systems analysis before reflecting on these and proposing a flexible, generic approach to collaborative systems analysis to be applied in the Pilots considered in the MYRIAD-EU project. Many of the reviewed approaches/tools share similarities, and this review has identified five broad categories of tools/approaches: (1) those that provide a conceptual framework from which to approach systems analysis, (2) those that focus on the development of system causal relationships, (3) those the focus more exclusively on system interdependencies, (4) those that serve primarily as visualization tools and can be combined with approaches from categories 1-3, (5) other approaches that do not fit into either of the above categories and do not generate conceptual system models.

We conclude that approaches that permit complete systems analyses offer the most promising reference points for the approach to be applied in MYRIAD-EU. Here we refer to the broad series of approaches and tools that support the mapping of different system components and their inter-linkages. These offer the benefits of effectively visualizing the key system functions and relationships (thereby improving (shared) system understanding), while also being geared towards supporting decision making.

Given these findings, we propose a collaborative multi-sector, multi-risk system analysis approach that is intended to satisfy the following requirements:

- It is capable of representing the holistic, integrated system and its key functions, risks, and opportunities.
- It highlights the key interdependencies and interactions between system components, including all feedbacks, trade-offs, and synergies.
- It generates a common, shared understanding of the integrated system and its objectives among Pilot stakeholders.
- It serves to prioritize key system functions, objectives, constraints, risks, and opportunities.
- It is flexible to the needs of the various Pilots and can encompass the incorporation of various supporting tools and approaches with which Pilot Leads are comfortable.

The proposed approach consists of the following three principal iterative steps:

1. Define system boundaries and constraints
2. Undertake sector-based analyses
3. Synthesise sector-based analyses into a whole-of-system analysis

Methods and tools are also proposed for each of the steps, however, these are to be treated as suggestions only. Pilot Leads are welcome to apply alternative methods and tools which they believe could assist in yielding the necessary information to define integrated decision contexts for their systems. To increase the usability of the material presented in this report, it is expected that its contents will be discussed with Pilot Leads in a dedicated meeting after its submission and prior to the first round of Pilot Workshops planned in months 13-15 (Sep-Nov 2022) within WP3. Moreover, the collaborative multi-sector, multi-risk system analysis approach described in this report will be further updated to incorporate insights and lessons learned from the experiences gained during these workshops.

Dissemination level of the document

- Public
- Restricted to other programme participants (including the Commission Services)
- Restricted to a group specified by the consortium (including the European Commission Services)
- Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the European Commission Services)

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1 Decision contexts in multi-risk settings

1.1 Interdependent complexities in multi-risk, multi-sector systems

Understanding the complexity of multi-hazard and multi-sector interactions is a significant scientific challenge, but there have been some recent attempts to create frameworks to identify these interactions and how they translate into risk for the concerned sectors. Accounting for multi-hazard risk means considering the interrelations between hazards and sectors in space and time, and how they can impact one another.

Previous work within the project (MYRIAD-EU D1.3 Part 2: Typologies of interdependencies between sectors) has sought to classify drivers of inter-sectoral dependence and develop typologies of inter-sectoral risk. Outcomes of this work have identified a set of four types of drivers/channels of inter-sectoral dependence and four multi-sector risk typologies.

The main drivers/channels of inter-sectoral dependence are;

- *Functional interdependence*: relating to situations where one system (e.g. sector) is connected to and relies on another system to operate. For example, the shutdown of a power station leading to the failure of nodes in a communication network.
- *Spatial interdependence*: referring to situations where spatial proximity leads to a correlated response in multiple systems (e.g. across multiple sectors). For example, the impacts of floods causing damage to local surrounding roads, severing transport links.
- *Financial interdependence*: which can refer to both top-down and bottom-up economic relationships. Top-down relationships refer to the majority of sector economic interdependencies where shared markets influence each other, e.g. investments, share prices, and availability of credit. Bottom-up relationships refer to situations in which responses to external events drive changes in the demand for goods and services, and thereby the financial markets, e.g. panic-buying in response to (perceived) shortages of goods during the COVID pandemic that drove up prices for those goods.
- *Social interdependence*: relates to the level of preparation and long-term planning by a community to face a natural hazard and encompasses concepts of vulnerability, adaptive capacity, and resilience. A community with high social capital is more likely to be resilient to disaster events. For example, in Bangladesh, farmers with strong mutual trust have had greater motivation to act to prevent potential disasters. In inter-sectoral settings, strong governance mechanisms between sectors with clearly defined roles and responsibilities help to build effective coping and adaptive capacity at both system- and sector-scales.

Similarly, for inter-sectoral risk, four multi-sector risk typologies have been identified:

- *Spill over*: where a hazard or event in one sector triggers events in other sectors in a monodirectional fashion. For example, a flood that causes power outages, the spread of dangerous pathogens from wastewater treatment plants, and halts industrial production thereby driving up prices.
- *Co-dependent*: where mutually dependent inter-sectoral functions lead to a 'canceling out' of both if one is negatively impacted. For example, water being needed to cool a power station to generate electricity, where that energy is needed to pump water through the distribution infrastructure to reach the power station.
- *Interacting intersecting*: Interacting intersecting risks are bidirectional (in contrast to spill over risks, above) and result from the intersection of two or more different risks. That is, two individual risks collide and lead to increased compound hazards. For example, the COVID-19 pandemic in combination with drought led to amplified compounded food security impacts of disrupted food distribution and reduced crop yields.
- *Independent intersecting*: Independent intersecting risks are those that result from an aggregation of multiple different impacts that when added together, have impacts that converge to create an accumulated risk elsewhere. For example, a disruption to transport

services combined with a lack of power supply can result in a completely separate risk in another sector, e.g. significant disruption to healthcare services as nurses and doctors are unable to get to work and healthcare machinery cannot function.

The development of a collaborative systems analysis approach for multi-risk should have the capacity to capture these dependencies in all their complexity.

1.2 Requirements for a collaborative systems analysis approach in a multi-risk setting

1.2.1 Why a collaborative systems approach?

There are several reasons for choosing a collaborative systems analysis approach for adaptive multi-risk, multi-sector decision making. Previous experiences of approaching complex problems through a sector-specific lens have taught us that this can lead to (unintended) negative consequences and impacts on other sectors. For example, consider the construction of a new reservoir for public drinking water supply that during drought periods leads to reduced stream flows for downstream agricultural producers and ecosystem services. Or - as during the recent COVID pandemic - public health measures that are put in place to curb the spread of a novel pathogen that indirectly negatively impact services, industry, and personal wellbeing. It is only by considering the system as a functioning whole that we can then formulate system-wide objectives that both recognize and balance the inherent trade-offs within our systems and allow us to devise and implement 'mutually beneficial' or so-called 'least cost' solutions that minimize negative impacts at the system scale. In doing so, we also ensure that system-wide resources, costs, and benefits can be distributed more efficiently and equitably in the pursuit of these objectives.

Hence, the principal purpose of employing systems analysis is to describe decision-making contexts in all their complexity. Instead of focusing on a single sector and its function(s), these approaches seek to describe how the integrated system functions as a whole, including its biophysical aspects, socioeconomic aspects, and institutional aspects as may be relevant to the set of challenges being addressed. The aim is to identify system constraints, interactions, and interdependencies that can be used to highlight any feedback loops, synergies, and trade-offs present in the system. These then help to highlight and make explicit for all actors the causal relationships between the various components in the system, which can then be used to identify and formulate strategies to mitigate challenges and exploit opportunities.

When dealing with complex multi-sector multi-risk systems, establishing a complete understanding of the system dynamics is not an easy task. Often the challenge becomes one of not simply ensuring that every system component is included, but rather of prioritizing these and making difficult choices relating to those which most greatly influence or impact system function. This includes both exogenous and endogenous drivers of risk in the system.

Collaboration (and negotiation) therefore plays a critical role in systems analysis approaches. System 'models' can only adequately and legitimately include those values, interests, and perspectives of those sectors or stakeholders which are represented in the analysis. Their priorities and interests can be promoted and negotiated while those of any which are absent can easily be neglected. Likewise, the involvement of a wide range of actors and interests can lead to the identification of novel and innovative cross-sector solutions that would otherwise not be considered in single-sector settings. It is therefore critical that any systems analysis process is founded upon sound principles of stakeholder analysis and engagement. In addition to allowing for the inclusion of a broad range of interests and perspectives, doing so reduces the potential for conflict to emerge between competing sectors by opening channels of communication, generating mutual understanding, and helping to negotiate compromise solutions. By developing and agreeing upon a common conceptual model of how a system functions, credible and effective solutions can then be identified and implemented with the support of all sectors and stakeholders.

1.2.2 Key users of the approach

In task T6.2 of WP6 within MYRIAD-EU, we aim to develop and provide guidance on a collaborative systems analysis approach to be applied in the Pilots that can fulfill the above-stated objectives. In terms of the application of the proposed approach, we have identified four key types of users:

- *Pilot Leads*: will be the primary means by which the proposed approach will be applied in each Pilot. Pilot Leads will serve as moderators or facilitators of the approach, coordinating the process of collaboration with Pilot stakeholders to develop common conceptual models, define system requirements and objectives, and then assess multi-risks and devise solutions and strategies to mitigate these.
- *Pilot stakeholders*: will be active participants in the approach, and it is their inputs that will be used to define the conceptual model, prioritize system objectives, formulate solutions and strategies and assess the system responses to these. They are ultimately the primary beneficiaries of the collaboratively developed shared vision and strategies.
- *MYRIAD-EU research partners*: will benefit from the experiences gained through the application of the approach in the Pilots, which will help to improve the approach by highlighting any weaknesses or aspects that require further elaboration.
- *Wider audience*: for those practitioners who are confronting multi-risk, multi-sector settings that share similarities to those in MYRIAD-EU, we hope they find value in employing collaborative systems analysis approaches when managing their situations. Similarly, for systems analysis practitioners, we hope they can learn from and benefit from the practical approach to systems analysis proposed in MYRIAD-EU.

1.2.3 Key features of the approach

Given the above, we aim to promote an approach that fulfills the following conditions for multi-sector, multi-risk systems:

- It is capable of representing the holistic, integrated system and its key functions, risks, and opportunities.
- It highlights the key interdependencies and interactions between system components, including all feedbacks, trade-offs, and synergies.
- It generates a common, shared understanding of the integrated system and its objectives among Pilot stakeholders.
- It serves to prioritize key system functions, objectives, constraints, risks, and opportunities.
- It is flexible to the needs of the various Pilots and can encompass the incorporation of various supporting tools and approaches with which Pilot leads are comfortable.

1.3 Purpose and structure of this document

This document intends to serve as a source of practical guidance to Pilot Leads in the delivery of the proposed approach in the Pilot workshops. Rather than prescribing a particular approach to be dogmatically followed, our goal is to propose a more flexible and generic set of iterative systems analysis process steps. These steps will be supported by those specific tools for stakeholder engagement and systems analysis with which Pilot Leads may already be familiar. This document is intended to serve as a 'living' document that will be further substantiated and elaborated based on additional insights gathered from the Pilots, stakeholders, and other consortium partners throughout MYRIAD-EU. It is also expected that its contents will be discussed with Pilot Leads in a dedicated meeting after its submission and prior to the first round of Pilot Workshops planned in months 13-15 (Sep-Nov 2022) within WP3.

The remainder of this document is structured as follows: Chapter 2 presents the findings of our literature review on promising approaches for collaborative systems analysis. Here we summarize the key features of the identified approaches and tools; their purposes, advantages, disadvantages, and limitations, and provide our initial assessment of their applicability within MYRIAD-EU. Chapter 3 reflects on the key takeaways from the preceding chapter, before outlining our proposed process for systems analysis in multi-sector, multi-risk systems. The process is

elaborated by a set of questions prompts to assist Pilot Leads in exploring and prioritizing system components and linkages together with stakeholders.

2 Promising approaches from literature

2.1 Introduction

This chapter presents the findings of our literature review on promising tools and approaches for collaborative systems analysis. The approaches and tools presented in the following sections involve varying degrees of systems thinking. This is the generic practice of examining a system (as a functioning whole) and its constituent elements, where these elements are presumed to be interacting with each other.

Many of the identified approaches/tools share similarities, and our review has identified five broad categories of tools/approaches: (1) those that provide a conceptual framework from which to approach systems analysis, (2) those that focus on the development of system causal relationships, (3) those the focus more exclusively on system interdependencies, (4) those that serve primarily as visualization tools and can be combined with other approaches, (5) other approaches that do not fit into either of the above categories and do not generate conceptual system models. The following sections deal with each of these categories in turn. Note that this list and the brief synopsis of each approach/tool should not be considered to be exhaustive and may be further substantiated and elaborated based on additional insights gathered from the Pilots, stakeholders, and other consortium partners throughout MYRIAD-EU.

[Appendix 1](#) provides a summary table of all approaches in terms of their key features, advantages, disadvantages, and limitations to their implementation.

2.2 Conceptual frameworks for systems analysis

The first identified category includes those approaches that provide conceptual frameworks from which to undertake systems analysis. That is, they do not stipulate a stepwise method or process to be followed, but rather provide an overarching generic framework that can be used to unpack how a system of concern functions, thereby helping to derive important causal relationships.

2.2.1 DIPSIR

DIPSIR (Drivers, Pressures, States, Impacts, Responses) framework (EC, 1999; [Figure 1](#)) is used for highlighting key relationships between social and environmental factors and can be used as a communication tool between researchers from different disciplines. It represents a structure of visualizing a system as a simple generic causal chain that commences with 'driving forces' (e.g. economic sectors, human activities), which generate 'pressures' (e.g. emissions, waste) that influence system 'states' (e.g. physical, chemical and biological), which generate 'impacts' on ecosystems, human health, and functions, and eventually lead to political 'responses' (prioritization, target setting, indicators). The transferability to multi-risk conceptualisation stems from the complexities of socio-ecological systems and organizing the elements potentially identified by the stakeholders in the predefined categories. DIPSIR has been widely applied to complex natural resource management problems as a means to unpack system elements and to develop a conceptual understanding of how social-ecological systems function.

Figure 1 DPSIR framework of causal relationships

2.2.2 Bow-Tie

The Bow-tie framework (Delvosalle et al., 2006, [Figure 2](#)) is used to analyze risk management practices and evaluate risk responses. It is centered on a critical event (or hazard), which is conceptualized as having a series of causes (fault tree, situated on the left) and consequences (event tree, situated on the right). It is a barrier-based approach that considers risk and its possible barriers that can either mitigate the causes or consequences of the critical event. Once a bow-tie has been structured, quantitative analyses can then be performed (if desired) by assigning probabilities to the primary events of the fault tree and the safety barriers of the event tree. Originally applied in the analysis of workplace accidents, it has been successfully applied in a range of industries including chemical, mining, rail, aviation, oil, and gas. Given its focus on the critical event, the bow-tie framework is most applicable in the analysis of cascading events and impacts within specific sectors and industries. It is less useful at representing more complex multi-sector system interactions.

Figure 2 Generic scheme of the bow tie (Delvosalle et al., 2006)

2.2.3 Strategic options and development analysis (SODA)

SODA (Ackerman and Eden, 2010) is based on cognitive (or causal) mapping, which allows for views to be captured and be structured in a "means-end" format that generates chains of argument. It enables a group or an individual to construct a graphical representation of a problematic situation in the form of outcome statements (e.g. "develop and deliver strategy for protected areas"), and thus explore options and their ramifications concerning a complex system of goals and objectives. Maps, in this case, are networks (directed graphs) comprising nodes (constructs/statements) and links (causal arrows). They can be viewed as representations of how an individual or a group interprets a situation and helps them make sense of it before considering action. The method aims to help groups arrive at a negotiated agreement about how to act to

resolve the situation. The approach is meant to emphasize both the process and the outcome of the collaboration between participants. Although it can encompass a broad range of system dimensions, its lack of any formal overarching structure can overwhelm participants who may find it too abstract.

2.3 Causal relationships

The second category focuses on the development and visualization of causal relationships within the system. These approaches all do so without providing any form of overarching conceptual framework from which to analyze these, but rather simply represent causality in different ways and levels of complexity, from simple linear chains, through to more complex loops, matrices, networks, or maps (Banitz et al., 2022). As such, they are broadly applicable across a wide range of domains and are particularly well-suited to the analysis of socio-ecological systems. Banitz et al. (2022) identify six challenges of visualizing complex causal relationships, which the various types of visualization are variously able or not to meet. These challenges include:

- Visualizing whether a relationship is causal, particularly when multiple factors are involved, and causality is difficult to discern.
- Visualizing the characteristics of causality, including positive and negative relationships.
- Visualizing reciprocal relationships
- Visualizing multiple causes
- Visualizing temporal dynamics of causal relationships
- Visualizing uncertainty around causal relationships

2.3.1 Linear causal chains

These aim to highlight the simple relations that exist within individual parts of the system and typically do not try to represent the system as a whole (Figure 3).

Figure 3 Linear causal chains (Banitz et al., 2022)

2.3.2 Dot and arrow diagrams

These aim to represent the system as a series of dots and arrows, where dots represent variables and arrows the inferred causality between them (Figure 4). Here, an additional restriction is placed on the diagram that only unidirectional arrows and no cycles or loops are permitted. Paths can be traced, and common challenges can be easily identified. Backdoor paths are those that lead from a subsequent variable back to a previous one in the chain, becoming a confounder in the relationship. An indirect path is formed by connecting two variables through a third variable, representing a mediator. This amounts to a robust causal diagram suitable for sectoral analysis. The directionality of the arrows is meant to present a certain order in which these events/variables affect one another, if that is uncertain then directionality can be relinquished.

Figure 4 Dot and arrow diagram for inferring causality (Banitz et al., 2022)

2.3.3 Causal loop diagrams

Causal loop diagrams (CLDs) are a popular means of visualizing causality and have been applied widely in natural resource management domains (e.g. Purwanto et al., 2019). They are a key tool in system dynamics approaches and aim to represent the system as a series of feedback loops involving two or more variables (Figure 5). In CLDs, directional arrows are also assigned a positive (reinforcing) or negative (balancing) relationship. This feature makes CLDs highly suitable for characterizing and visualizing reciprocal causal relationships. Linking multiple loops can be used to create a more concise understanding of a particular problem and help illuminate the spillover effects from one system to another.

Figure 5 Causal loop diagram (Banitz et al., 2022)

Network diagrams have two types of elements, nodes (objects) and edges (lines that link the objects), these diagrams can be used to describe abstract structural aspects of systems (Figure 6). Nodes usually represent elements of the same category, i.e. individuals, organizations, spatial areas, and events, although this is not an absolute requirement. Meanwhile, edges can represent proximity, flows, interactions, or association between elements, and can be assigned both weights or directionality (or neither). This type of diagram aims to derive causation from the network structure, which is used to identify vulnerabilities and bottlenecks generated by the number and distribution of nodes and edges.

Figure 6 Network diagram (Banitz et al., 2022)

2.3.4 Group Model Building

Group model building refers to a participatory method whereby stakeholders are guided to collaboratively develop a conceptual causal loop diagram of their system for the purposes of decision-making. Here the focus is not only on the visualization of the system, but also on the structured participatory processes behind the development of this model. It aims to generate a shared understanding of a system and its challenges by aligning perceptions (problem framing), elucidating variables, and developing mitigation strategies based on the dynamics present in the system. Originally applied in organizational settings and in combination with system dynamics software simulations (Vennix, 1996), it is now commonly used in natural resource settings as a qualitative modeling tool (e.g. Purwanto et al., 2019) and with a range of quantitative simulation tools.

2.4 System interdependencies

The third category of tools focus less on general causal relationships but more on the interdependencies between a specified set of system components, for example, sectors, and actors. processes, hazards. Here the nature of the interdependency is not explicitly captured in the visualization medium, but simply the existence of the interdependency itself.

2.4.1 Circle

Critical Infrastructures: Relations and Consequences for Life and Environment (Circle, Deltares, 2022) is an online open tool that can be used interactively with stakeholders. It has traditionally been applied in workshop settings to assess the vulnerability of infrastructure to the cascading impacts of flooding events. Is useful for visualizing the existence of interactions between system components in data-poor environments (Figure 7), and therefore lacks some of the information needed for an in-depth systems analysis when considered in isolation. Additional complexity must be captured through detailed note-taking of stakeholder discussions as the Circle diagram is generated. It is often applied in combination with quantitative physical system (e.g. flooding) simulation models to visualize the impacts of the cascading effects.

Figure 7 Circle diagram (Deltares, 2022)

2.4.2 Regional interaction frameworks

Regional interaction frameworks (Gill et al. 2020), can help in understanding the multi-hazard environment of specific spatial events. It aims to determine potential natural hazard interactions and to depict hazard cascades via a matrix form (Figure 8). It is an extensive approach, which integrates gathering evidence from a diverse range of sources, including literature, field observations, interviews, and workshops. It is an easily scalable approach, working at both global, regional, and local scales with information at different resolutions. As with Circle, the tool itself

does not entail analysis of the nature of the interactions between hazards or any necessary thresholds, but merely the existence of the interaction.

Figure 8 Regional hazard interaction matrix illustrating a hazard cascade (Gill et al., 2020)

2.5 (Online) visualization tools

The fourth category of tools reflects those that serve as supporting tools to other approaches for systems analysis and assist in the development of system diagrams. There has been an explosion in online digital diagrammatic tools in recent years. These now mean that system diagrams can be easily developed in both remote and face-to-face settings.

2.5.1 Digital whiteboards

Simple visualizations can be manually generated using online collaborative whiteboard applications (e.g. Miro, Mural, MS Whiteboard, etc.). These typically share common features such as the ability to place shapes, text boxes, images, and (virtual) post-its on a canvas and join these elements together with lines and arrows. Most importantly, they offer the ability for multiple users to collaborate in real-time in the development of the diagram on the canvas, which is well-suited to collaborative mapping sessions. Most of these collaborative tools, however, require a license to access or unlock their full feature sets.

2.5.2 Digital drawing tools

More sophisticated system diagrams can be created using digital drawing tools (e.g. draw.io, Visio, etc.). These applications are typically focused on generating specific types of diagrams such as organization charts, flow charts, process diagrams, maps, or networks. In most instances,

however, these tools lack the collaboration element, which means their use in participatory settings needs to be mediated by a single user.

2.5.3 Collaborative digital drawing tools

A final family of tools (e.g. Kumu, Lucidchart, Creately) seeks to combine the advantages of the preceding two paragraphs. They offer digital visualization tools to map systems, stakeholders, community assets, concepts, and networks. Multiple users can collaborate in real-time in the development of their system maps or can in some instances generate maps from imported tabulated data. A variety of diagram types can be generated, including stakeholder maps, systems maps, causal loop diagrams, community asset maps, and concept maps. A downside of many of these tools is that they require a license to either access or unlock the majority of their feature sets.

2.6 Additional systems approaches

The final category belongs to a set of approaches that can be combined with systems mapping to enhance understanding of uncertainties in the system elements and the links between them. The following approaches present methods that do not result in systems maps or conceptual models, but rather elaborate on specific issues, such as problem definition, or aim to generate consensus and understand the viewpoints of participating stakeholders.

2.6.1 Q Methodology

Q methodology (Stephenson, 1953, Raadgever et al, 2008)) can be used to study significantly different viewpoints within a given population about a particular topic. It is geared towards correlating patterns of respondent thoughts, where the respondents are the variables. The process debuts with collecting statements on a topic during exploratory interviews, these are then rephrased and articulated being then distributed to stakeholders, this is achieved through online surveys in which the participants express their level of agreement and alignment with the statements. The aim is to capture the correlating patterns of thoughts of the respondents, resulting in clusters of majority and minority viewpoints.

2.6.2 Soft systems methodology

Soft systems methodology (SSM, Checkland and Scholes, 1990) serves as a tool for eliciting knowledge on the context in which the whole system functions (Magsood et al, 2001). Its objective is to learn about the structures, processes, perceptions, and beliefs associated with the problem context, which it gathers from the different individuals involved in the situation. It may be used to analyze any problem or situation, but it is most appropriate where the problem "cannot be formulated as a search for an efficient means of achieving a defined end; a problem in which ends, goals, purposes are themselves problematic" (Checkland, 1999, p. 316). The approach stimulates debate and captures participants' vision for the future and allows for the exploitation of individual and socially constructed group knowledge and experience.

2.6.3 Strategic assumptions and group testing

Strategic assumptions and group testing (SAST, Mitroff & Emshoff, 1979) are designed to be used in situations where problems are highly interrelated and often conceal deep divisions between those addressing the problems. This methodology can be regarded as having four major stages in which groups are formed, assumptions about a topic are surfaced, group views are consolidated separately, before these are synthesized through dialectical debate. The approach is strategy-oriented and does not explicitly involve systems exploration.

2.6.4 Strategic choice approach

The strategic choice approach (SCA) is a balanced collection of tools and concepts developed to facilitate communication about the structuring of perplexing decision problems, and also about strategies for making progress toward timely commitments to agreed actions (Friend, 2011). The

principal output of work takes the form of a decision graph, in which significant connections between pairs of decision areas have been identified in the form of decision links. Where there are many interlinked decision areas, a subset of these is selected as an agreed problem focus before proceeding to develop and compare possible actions. The process of comparison fleshes out sources of uncertainty and considers the overall impact of uncertainty on decisions, leading to a discussion of opportunities for managing the most critical areas of uncertainty in a collaborative way. It has been traditionally used for decision-making within organizations, and emphasizes facilitating decisions, managing uncertainty, sustaining progress, structuring communication, and guiding collaboration.

2.6.5 Scenario Planning

Scenario planning (as presented by Butler et al. 2016) is a popular and flexible tool used to inform anticipatory adaptation by providing descriptions rather than forecasts or predictions of plausible futures that reflect different perceptions on development. In multi-stakeholder settings they can act as objects to promote social learning and collective action and as reference points for development planning. It encompasses several overarching steps that examine understanding surrounding drivers of change, possible futures, and desired development paths, and no regret strategies. In a stakeholder involvement setting, it represents a lengthy approach and can be seen as the first step in long-term capacity building.

2.6.6 Critical Scenario Method

Developing scenario planning, the critical scenario method (Cairns et al. 2010) represents another means of conducting a group exercise that involves both broad and deep research on an issue, making sense of all the material in relation to each other. It commences with the identification of driving forces, i.e. social, technological, economic, political, legal, and ecological. It then proceeds with discussions of the relationships between factors and in developing scenario storylines. Best and worst scenarios are paired, and desired developments are identified, and further questions are asked. The approach was initially proposed to suit international business models, such that it promotes a winner-loser mentality that may not apply to all fields.

2.6.7 Adaptive capacity wheels

Adaptive capacity wheels can enhance adaptive capacity by identifying strong and weak areas within specific institutions (Gupta et al. 2010). The focus of this tool is firmly on adaptation and institutional capacities, rather than complete system analysis. Categories are devised and scored to assess institutional adaptive capacity in a qualitative and semi-qualitative way. The main categories assessed are variety, learning capacity, room for autonomous change, leadership, resources, and fair governance. These are then subdivided into sub-categories intended to evaluate different aspects of institutional performance. The approach could potentially be translated and adapted to suit sectoral analysis or institutional approaches to multi-risk management.

3 Collaborative systems analysis in multi-risk settings

3.1 Introduction

This chapter reflects on the key takeaways from the preceding chapter, particularly in terms of their relevance to multi-sector, multi-risk settings, before outlining our proposed flexible approach for systems analysis to be undertaken in MYRIAD-EU.

3.2 Reflections on existing approaches and tools for collaborative systems analysis

Chapter 2 presented a wide variety of tools and approaches that have been applied to varying degrees in systems analysis. Some approaches provide an overarching conceptual framework of analysis. Some support analyses of complete systems, while others focus more on particular aspects or sub-systems only. Many attempts to visually represent the system as a series of components linked by arrows, while others deal mainly with descriptive stakeholder perceptions. Several approaches are also explicitly linked to specific methods of quantitative simulation and

analysis; however, this is by no means a precondition for the deployment of these approaches for conceptual modeling purposes. In MYRIAD-EU, where sector and stakeholder profiles, problem domains, and specific assessment tools vary across the Pilots, we identify a requirement for approaches and tools which offer sufficient flexibility to adapt to the different contexts. It is for this reason we see value in highlighting approaches that support the development of visual conceptual models, which may later be translated across to the specific simulation and assessment tools applied in each pilot.

Given the objective of MYRIAD-EU is to assess multi-sector, multi-risk settings, we conclude that the approaches which permit complete systems analyses offer the most promising reference points. Here we refer to the broad series of approaches and tools that support the mapping of different system components and linking them with their causal relationships. These offer the benefits of effectively visualizing the key system functions and relationships, thereby improving (shared) system understanding, while in some instances also explicitly being geared towards supporting decision making (e.g. group model building). The set of approaches/tools focused exclusively on system interactions (e.g. Circle, Regional Interaction Frameworks) may also be useful to unpack the presence of interdependencies present within each pilot but should be used in combination with more complete analysis approaches.

Our review of the existing approaches and tools for collaborative systems analysis also suggests that when dealing with complex integrated systems, there can be a need to structure the analysis through the application of a common conceptual framework (e.g. DPSIR, bow-tie). This can then be used to sequentially map out system components and establish causal relationships. System analyses also often rely on repeat iterations to capture all components and relationships to the required level of complexity. In many cases, this includes examining relevant sub-systems sequentially before identifying the interrelationships between these (e.g. biophysical, socioeconomic, institutional systems). Finally, once a conceptual system model has been developed, it can be used to guide ensuing processes of objectives setting, and the identification of decision-making indicators (e.g. as in group model building). When done well, these types of conceptual models are capable of guiding stakeholder discussions towards the identification of (innovative) potential solutions.

3.3 Proposed collaborative systems analysis approach to be applied in MYRIAD-EU

We have attempted to incorporate the desirable 'features' outlined in the preceding section into a flexible and generic collaborative systems analysis approach for multi-sector, multi-risk settings in MYRIAD-EU. We, therefore, propose the following iterative, stepwise process to define the decision context in each of the Pilots ([Figure 9](#)). Broadly, the process consists of 3 main steps:

1. Defining system boundaries and constraints
2. Undertaking sector-based analyses (if appropriate)
3. Synthesizing sector-based analyses into a whole system analysis

Figure 9 Proposed collaborative systems analysis approach to be applied in MYRIAD-EU

Although these steps are presented sequentially, the expectation is that the analysis process will be highly iterative. For example, performing the sector-based analyses may reveal that any earlier defined system boundaries and constraints may need to be redefined or further elaborated. Or it may be that in performing the system-scale synthesis that components present in some sector sub-systems are recognized to have been omitted from others, demanding further elaboration. But this is the nature of systems analysis; the aim is to structure the process as far as possible while recognizing that building a system model can often feel messy and unstructured.

The following sections further detail the information to be gathered during each step of the process. Methods and tools are also proposed to assist in this regard, however, these are to be treated as suggestions only. Pilot Leads are welcome to apply alternative methods and tools which they believe could assist in yielding the necessary information to define integrated decision contexts for the system as a whole.

Note also that the approach has been designed with large group settings in mind. That is, we have presented an approach where breakout groups of sector-specific stakeholders make sense, which results in a process whereby Steps 2 and 3 are completed as separate activities (Step 2 in breakouts, Step 3 in plenary). In smaller group settings with few stakeholders, it would equally be appropriate to combine Steps 2 & 3 in the one conceptual modeling exercise. In this case, each sector could still be dealt with in turn as the whole-of-system model is gradually built up collaboratively. The approach is intended to be flexible and Pilot Leads should adapt it to the practical realities of each stakeholder group.

3.3.1 Step 1: System Boundaries and Constraints

The first step of the proposed systems analysis approach is to define the system boundaries and constraints. The purpose of this step is to initially specify limits to the complexity of the system to be unpacked during later steps. In defining system boundaries, key considerations should include its spatial extent, temporal extent and resolution (i.e. planning time horizons), sectors to be included, and an initial consideration of key system functions (biophysical, socioeconomic, institutional), characteristics, and constraints (example functions are available in Table 1). An initial consideration of the key hazards and risks to the system should also be carried out to

ensure that all represented stakeholders agree on the (multi-)hazards to be addressed by MYRIAD-EU. Note that it is not the intention to map out every possible element and relationship present in the system, but rather to prioritize these according to the core issue(s) being addressed.

Table 1 Example system functions, characteristics and constraints for biophysical, socioeconomic and institutional sub-systems

	Bio-physical	Socio-economic	Institutional
Functions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Rainfall, river discharge - Earthquakes - Heat regulation - Primary production - Hazards, e.g. extreme weather, flooding, pandemic 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Water supply - Flood protection - Food production - Energy production - Tourism services - Transportation - Health services - Recreational services, e.g. fishing, swimming, hiking - Financial crisis 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Governance responsibilities - Subsidies - Penalties/fines - Hazards, e.g. state capture, corruption
Characteristics	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Self-regulating - Suffering scarcity or degradation 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Social values, e.g. allowable water use, transportation preferences, dietary requirements - Economic dependencies, e.g. supply chains 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Hierarchies, between and within institutions - Institutional dependencies, e.g. transport fines that fund road improvements
Constraints	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Resource availability, e.g. water, wind, soil - Environmental requirements (e.g. e-flows, maintenance of biodiversity) - Temperature patterns - Rainfall patterns 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Demands, e.g. water, energy, food, transport - Minimum production limits 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Regulatory limits - Jurisdictional boundaries - Planning controls/zoning

Potential questions to pose during this step include:

- What are the limits to the area/topic/challenge that we are going to consider/assess?
- What is the core purpose of each of the represented sectors in terms of overall system function? For example, the energy sector provides energy to power services and produce goods, the water sector provides flood protection, etc.
- What are the key pieces of infrastructure that are related to each sector? Where are these located?
- What are the key socioeconomic functions that relate to each sector? For example, the tourism sector serves to drive local economies, the shipping sector serves to deliver goods, the health sector serves to maintain a healthy society, etc. Where are these key socioeconomic functions located (if possible)?
- What are the key institutional constraints relating to core system functions? For example, are there any legal requirements or regulatory limits which must be adhered to?
- What are the key system challenges and hazards that we are aiming to address in MYRIAD-EU? Where are the impacts from these most felt?
- What time horizons are we interested in for planning? Have we sufficiently considered long-term impacts? Do the time horizons match well with the anticipated timescales for the hazard impacts we aim to mitigate?

In terms of methods, several tools can be applied to support these discussions. One of the simplest tools to stimulate stakeholder discussions is a *collaborative geographical mapping exercise*. A map of the area is placed in front of stakeholders and they are set the task of situating key (physical) features on it. Stakeholders are prompted to locate the physical aspects of core system functions and critical infrastructure on the map (e.g. energy plants and substations, water treatment plants, ports, priority industries, etc), before identifying locations where impacts from the identified hazards are primarily experienced. Both digital and hard copy maps can be used for this purpose, depending on whether the session is taking place virtually or face-to-face. If taking place virtually, we suggest pasting a picture of an existing map of the area in a digital whiteboard environment (e.g. Mural, Miro, MS Whiteboard) that then allows participants to actively engage and place icons, shapes, or comments directly on the map. In face-to-face settings, markers, stickers, post-its, and the like can be deployed in the same way.

For the non-physical elements of the system, an initial ‘Circle’-type analysis could be performed to identify the initial set of linkages assumed to exist between system sectors, functions, characteristics, and constraints. In Circle analyses, system components are placed around the outside of a circle, before any links are established between them (Figure 2). Again, these types of analyses can be performed using digital or paper-based drawing and visualization tools. In these analyses, it is the existence of the link that is important to visualize, rather than the precise nature of the link (although it should nevertheless be noted down).

It is important to keep in mind that the critical outcome of step 1 is to get stakeholders talking about their system and to develop an initial set of ideas about how its various components are related to each other. It is therefore recommended to also assign a dedicated notetaker to capture any additional (e.g. non-spatial, non-visualized) information to be gathered from the responses to the facilitated discussion points above. Table 2 summarizes the information presented in the preceding paragraphs.

Table 2 Step 1: Objectives and (suggested) methods

Objective	Suggested Method(s)
Broadly define systems in terms of: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Space - Sectors to include - System functions, characteristics and constraints (physical, social, institutional) - Planning time horizon and resolution - Challenges/hazards 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Geographical mapping exercise (initial quick scan) <ol style="list-style-type: none"> a) A collaborative geographical map of the pilot area is produced b) Sectors and physical location of key system functions are placed on (virtual) map c) Physical locations of identified hazards placed on map (where possible) 2. Facilitated group discussion, supported by Circle analysis to establish simple linkages between system components <ol style="list-style-type: none"> a) Elaborate physical system functions with initial set of social/institutional functions/characteristics/constraints b) Establish appropriate planning time horizon and resolution, given sector, function and hazard profile

3.3.2 Step 2: Sector sub-system analyses

In the second step - and in light of the system boundary conditions and constraints that were defined in Step 1 - the aim is to analyze each sector sub-system separately and develop the conceptual model for how it functions in isolation. The task is to elaborate the broad system outline developed in step 1 with the specific complexities of relevance to each sector sub-system,

particularly in terms of its physical, socioeconomic, and institutional characteristics and constraints, its key actors and their agency, and the specific impacts of the (previously) identified system-wide hazards and risks. Additional sector-specific challenges, hazards, and risks can also be included at this stage, especially where system-level hazards cascade to additional sector-specific hazards (e.g. via multi-hazard impact relations). Outputs from WP5 on the multi-risk scenarios to be applied can also be introduced and considered in this step. By analyzing each sector sub-system in isolation, the aim is to gradually build up the whole system model from the 'bottom-up', rather than trying to dive deeply into the more abstract and complex system as a whole. The expectation is that sector stakeholders hold expertise on how their system functions, whereas their knowledge of the complexity of the complete system may be more limited. Note that in undertaking the sector analyzes exogenous factors and components of relevance to other subsystems may also be included (e.g. for water supply sub-system: economic growth, climate change, energy supply, etc.), but the system as a whole is not being considered in this step. The knowledge and understanding developed on dynamic sectoral feedbacks within WP4 can also be brought in to inform the analysis.

Following the development of each sector's conceptual model, sector stakeholders must then use this model to derive/refine a limited and prioritized set of sector objectives and indicators. These should be developed for each of the planning time horizons that were specified in Step 1 (e.g. short-term, mid-term, long-term). Objectives should be framed in such a way as to focus on the core outcomes that the sector is trying to achieve (e.g. supply sufficient energy to society to support economic growth, protect energy supplies from hazards, drive energy sector climate mitigation efforts, etc.). The key is to focus on trying to answer the question 'How does each sector succeed?', with the resulting objectives being those that would enjoy widespread societal support (i.e. are largely uncontroversial). Once the set of objectives has been formulated, these are then translated across to a set of SMART (specific, measurable, assignable, realistic, and time-based) indicators, even if the later assessment will be qualitative in nature (e.g. zero unmet energy demand (MW), energy substations protected from floods to (future) 1:100 flood level, supply x MW renewable energy by 2030).

Potential questions to pose during this step include:

- How does this sector succeed?
- How can we measure this success?
- What other factors influence sector success?
- What factors influence these factors?
- What factors are necessary to support the core sector functions?
- What factors can we identify that stress core sector functions?
- What are the key biophysical functions that relate to this sector? e.g., wave height, sea level rise, storm surge, wave dissipation
- What are the key socioeconomic functions that relate to this sector? e.g. flood protection, income generation
- What are the key institutional enablers and constraints relating to core sector functions? e.g. planning controls, DRR governance structures
- How are all the preceding considerations linked?
- Have we considered exogenous drivers of change in our sector?
- How do the identified system hazards influence sector functions?
- What additional sector-specific hazards can we identify that influence sector functions? Are these in any way linked?
- Are there any functional, spatial, financial, or societal interdependencies or multi-hazard impact relations that we need to consider (refer to the separate table of questions listed in [Appendix 2](#))?

This type of analysis similarly lends itself to several tools and approaches available in the literature. While we do not recommend a specific tool/methodology, the output from this step should preferably be a visual representation of the sector sub-system conceptual model. As

indicated in section 3.2, many of the approaches and tools identified in the literature are capable of generating conceptual models that consist of system components linked by arrows. Pilot Leads should select tools/methodologies with which they (and their co-facilitators) feel most comfortable, which could range from the more sophisticated purpose-built digital tools (e.g. Kumu, Vensim), to simpler manual (digital, physical) whiteboard representations composed with post-its and (hand-)drawn arrows. The key is to unpack how each sector functions in detail and to uncover the *causal relationships* between each of the system factors (e.g. Figure 10). Here, the first four steps of the *DPSI* framework (Figure 1) may be useful to unpack and identify the drivers, pressures, and sub-system states that relate to the corresponding sector impact (i.e. objective). The process applied in Group Model Building-type approaches to identify components, causes, consequences, and feedback loops may also be useful (Figure 11). Whatever method is employed, causal relationships may be constructed in the form of chains, loops, matrices, or webs as per the preference of the Pilot Leads. What is important is to generate a common, shared understanding of how each sector sub-system functions for the relevant stakeholders, and to a resolution and level of complexity that matches with the system-scale analysis.

Figure 10 Example causal loop diagram for water management (Source: Felfelani et al., 2013)

Figure 11 The process of causal loop diagram development (Source: Purwanto et al., 2019)

For the prioritization of system objectives, the conceptual model can be used to conduct a simple voting exercise together with relevant sector stakeholders. This can either be performed through a show of hands or via an exercise where each stakeholder is given a limited number of ‘tokens’ (e.g. stickers) which they can allocate across the identified objectives. The aim is to rank each objective in terms of its importance relative to each other. Table 3 summarizes the information presented in the preceding paragraphs.

Table 3 Step 2: Objectives and (suggested) methods

Objective	Suggested Method(s)
<p>Given system boundary conditions and map, elaborate each sector sub-system in terms of:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Sub-system functions and characteristics (physical, social, institutional) - Key actors and agency - Impacts of challenges/hazards on sector functions, including multi-hazard impact relations 	<p>1. Conceptual modelling exercise, e.g. develop Causal Loop Diagram using (virtual) post-its, Kubu or other online tool. Each sector builds own conceptual model of its sub-system:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> a) Conceptually map each sub-system function. Can use DPSI to frame discussions b) How are the functions linked? What additional (linking) characteristics do we need to include? c) Conceptually map relevant challenges/hazards that impact sub-system function d) How are the challenges/hazards linked to the functions/characteristics? What additional (linking) characteristics do we need to include? e) Are there any multi-hazard impact relations that also need to be considered?
<p>Based on the above, derive (limited, prioritised) set of sub-system objectives & indicators at different time horizons</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Short term - Medium term - Long term 	<p>2. Setting objectives (facilitated group discussion)</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> a) What is the main objective relating to each function, hazard/challenge for each of the three time horizons? <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • How does each function succeed? b) Prioritisation. How can the respective objectives be ranked? Each participant is given e.g. 5 votes to allocate to their priority objectives. Results are tallied to establish priority sector-based objectives <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • How does the sector succeed? • How do we measure this success? • What are the main influences on this success (update conceptual model if necessary)?

3.3.3 Step 3: System-scale synthesis

In the final step, all of the individual sector-based conceptual models are then analyzed for any components which can be translated across to an integrated whole-of-system model. Here the aim is not to necessarily translate all sector-specific complexity across to the system model, but rather to identify those components that are central to the functioning of the complete system. The task is therefore to harmonize and synthesize the outputs developed in Step 2 and to formulate the system-wide conceptual model that includes all relevant interactions and interdependencies between the sectors, including multi-hazard impact relationships. The output from this step should preferably be a visual representation of the system-wide conceptual model. This should again incorporate relevant outputs from WP4 and WP5 relating to the multi-risk scenarios to be applied and their dynamic system feedback.

Following the development of the system-wide model, this is then used in combination with the prioritized lists of sector objectives to derive the prioritized set of system-wide objectives and indicators. Again, these should be developed for each of the planning time horizons that were specified in Step 1 (e.g. short-term, mid-term, long-term). The key is to focus on trying to answer the question 'How does our system succeed?', with the resulting objectives again being those that would enjoy widespread societal support (i.e. are uncontroversial). As in step 2, these objectives are then translated across to a set of SMART indicators.

Potential questions to pose during this step include:

- What sub-system components are common to multiple sectors?
- What uncommon sub-system components can be ignored at the system scale?
- What uncommon sub-system components cannot be ignored but remain central to system function?
- How are all these factors linked to each other?
- Are there any additional components that we need to include in light of these linkages?
- Does our model capture all the key biophysical functions that relate to the system?
- Does our model capture all the key socioeconomic functions that relate to the system?
- Does our model capture all the key institutional enablers and constraints that relate to the system?
- How does the system succeed?
- How can we measure this success?
- Are there any additional functional, spatial, financial, or societal interdependencies or multi-hazard impact relations that we need to consider at the system scale (refer to the separate table of questions listed in [Appendix 2](#))?

The methods applied in this step are largely similar to those of the preceding steps. Ideally, the chosen method should match with that which has been applied in Step 2, as then many of the existing relationships present in those models can be simply translated across to the whole-of-system model. But it may be that a simpler approach is needed, in which case a repeat of the Circle-type analysis completed in Step 1 with the harmonized/ synthesized set of system components used to establish an updated set of system dependencies. Table 4 summarizes the information presented in the preceding paragraphs.

Table 4 Step 3: Objectives and (suggested) methods

Objective	Suggested Method(s)
<p>Given core sub-system/sector <u>functions</u>, identify the synergies/interactions/dependencies between the sub-systems</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Functional • Financial • Societal • Spatial <p>Also, identify any additional multi-hazard impact relations between the sectors</p>	<p>1. OPTIONS:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Synthesised CLD from sector models to create single system-wide conceptual mode <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ What are common elements (inc. hazards) to all sector models? ○ What uncommon elements can be ignored (to simplify complexity) at the system scale? Which elements cannot be ignored? ○ How do the various sector-specific elements link to other sector elements? ○ Are there any additional multi-hazard impact relations that also need to be considered? • Reperform Circle-type analysis with prioritised system components to establish linkages between stakeholders/sectors <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Detailed note-taking on discussions to establish additional complexity
<p>Given core sub-system/sector <u>objectives</u>, what are the synergies and trade-offs between these? Derive set of prioritised system-level objectives & indicators at different time horizons</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Short term - Medium term - Long term 	<p>2. Setting objectives (facilitated group discussion)</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> a) From the set of prioritised sector objectives: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Are there any common objectives? b) Prioritisation. How can the respective sector objectives be ranked? Each participant is given e.g. 5 votes to allocate to their priority system objectives. Results are tallied to establish priority system objectives <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • How does the system succeed? • How do we measure this success? • What are the main influences on this success (update conceptual model if necessary)?

When the application of these steps will require information from stakeholders, the ethics principles and data management guidelines will be adopted as they are described in the D8.1 Quality Ethics Risk Management Plan and D8.3 Data Management Plan.

4 Conclusion

Collaborative systems analysis approaches are needed for forward-looking adaptive multi-risk decision making for a variety of reasons, including (i) to avoid negative consequences when approaching problems through a sector-specific lens, (ii) to aid in the formulation of system-wide objectives that both recognize and balance the inherent trade-offs within our systems, (iii) to ensure a more equitable distribution of system-wide resources, costs and benefits, and (iv) to help reduce the potential for stakeholder conflict. In this light, the principal purpose of collaborative systems analysis approaches is to help describe decision-making contexts in all their complexity.

This brief report has presented the findings of a literature review on promising tools and approaches for collaborative systems analysis. These informed the formulation of a proposed flexible, generic approach to collaborative systems analysis for application in the MYRIAD-EU Pilots.

Our review identified five broad categories of tools/approaches: (1) those that provide a conceptual framework from which to approach systems analysis, (2) those that focus on the development of system causal relationships, (3) those the focus more exclusively on system interdependencies, (4) those that serve primarily as visualization tools and can be combined with approaches from categories 1-3, (5) other approaches that do not fit into either of the above categories and do not generate conceptual system models. We conclude that approaches that permit complete systems analyses offer the most promising reference points for the approach to be applied in MYRIAD-EU. Here we refer to the broad series of approaches and tools that support the mapping of different system components and their inter-linkages. These offer the benefits of effectively visualizing the key system functions and relationships (thereby improving (shared) system understanding), while also being geared towards supporting decision making.

Given these findings, we propose a collaborative multi-sector, multi-risk system analysis approach intended to satisfy the following requirements:

- It is capable of representing the holistic, integrated system and its key functions, risks, and opportunities.
- It highlights the key interdependencies and interactions between system components, including all feedbacks, trade-offs, and synergies.
- It generates a common, shared understanding of the integrated system and its objectives among Pilot stakeholders.
- It serves to prioritize key system functions, objectives, constraints, risks, and opportunities.
- It is flexible to the needs of the various Pilots and can encompass the incorporation of various supporting tools and approaches with which Pilot Leads are comfortable.

The proposed approach consists of the following three principal iterative steps:

1. Define system boundaries and constraints
2. Undertake sector-based analyses
3. Synthesise sector-based analyses into a whole-of-system analysis

Each step has been elaborated with a set of suggested methods and tools, however, these are to be treated as suggestions only. Pilot Leads are welcome to apply alternative methods and tools which they believe could assist in yielding the necessary information to define integrated decision contexts for their systems. The collaborative multi-sector, multi-risk system analysis approach described in this report will be further updated to incorporate insights and lessons learned from the stakeholder engagement undertaken at the first round of Pilot Workshops planned in months 13-15 (Sept-Nov 2022) within WP3.

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Appendix 1: Table of identified tools and approaches

Tool/approach	Description including phases of use	Application e.g. hazards	Advantages	Disadvantages	Limitations/ Learning Curve	Time taken	More information
Circle	<p>Helps stakeholders understand the complex and interdependent relations between critical infrastructure systems. Uses the Online Circle tool, and is often combined with physical system (e.g. flooding) simulation models to visualize the impacts of cascading effects.</p> <p>1) Circle uses (verbal) information provided by workshop participants to identify system dependencies between critical infrastructure not present in the public domain.</p> <p>2) Results are presented to participants in an interactive game model.</p> <p>3) Participants examine different adaptation methods in order to increase resilience to climatic events.</p>	<p>Can be employed objectively (physical hazards) as well as subjectively in terms of resilience and risk perception.</p> <p>Typically used to understand the impacts of flooding on infrastructure.</p>	<p>Useful for understanding critical infrastructure and cascading impacts.</p> <p>Collaborative tool that encourages synergy between stakeholders.</p> <p>Works in a data-poor environment i.e. causal links can be visualised without detailed information.</p> <p>Provides rapid visualization.</p> <p>Is Deltares software, such that expertise exists within MYRIAD-EU in relation to its use.</p>	<p>Visualises the existence of system interactions, but not the nature of those interactions, which must be captured through note-taking of stakeholder discussions.</p>	<p>Circle tool is online and works best in combination with a TouchTable or projector.</p> <p>Online tool has been designed with ease-of-use in mind, but may require some practice.</p> <p>There is also a version which can be used without online resources (Circle Bao), but access to materials may be difficult</p> <p>Guidance document exists for application of offline Bao version.</p>	3 hours (workshop)	<p>Circle Software</p> <p>Deltares</p>

Tool/approach	Description including phases of use	Application e.g. hazards	Advantages	Disadvantages	Limitations/ Learning Curve	Time taken	More information
DIPSIR	The DIPSIR (Drivers, Pressures, States, Impacts, Responses) framework highlights key relationships between social and environmental factors and can be used as a communication tool between researchers from different disciplines. It proposes that to understand socio-economic and ecological systems five key components are needed: driving forces and their resulting pressures on environmental and socioeconomic states, the impacts resulting from these and societal responses.	Often used in natural resources management, e.g. DPSIR models of coastal systems have been largely used to support and develop conceptual understanding of coastal social-ecological systems and to identify drivers and pressures in the coastal realm.	Good for assessing complex natural resource issues i.e. fluctuating complex aquatic ecosystems and relationships to surrounding populations. Good for merging natural and social sciences.	Social and justice issues tend to come as an afterthought (Gupta et al, 2019). Discrepancies in application due to same variables being placed under different categories. Can lead to an oversimplification of cause-effect relationships- need for more complex, nested, conceptual models. Only a limited number of studies have used DPSIR as a starting point for semi-quantitative or quantitative analyses, but there is potential for transformative quantitative analyses and transdisciplinary applications of the DPSIR framework.	Not especially risk related. No clear outline/ structure of how to implement	1 day (understanding complex system)	Using a DPSIR framework to support good natural resource management and policy - Learning for Sustainability

Tool/approach	Description including phases of use	Application e.g. hazards	Advantages	Disadvantages	Limitations/ Learning Curve	Time taken	More information
Bow-Tie	<p>A visual tool to keep an overview of risk management practices and evaluate risk responses. Considers risk and its possible barriers. Starts with accident causes and ends with consequences, all being centered on a critical hazard or event. Composed of FT (fault tree) on left identifying possible events (primary and intermediate) causing the top event and an event tree (ET) on right-hand side showing possible consequences of critical events based on failure or success of safety barriers.</p> <p>Once the Bow Tie model is constructed, quantitative information can be applied by assigning probabilities to primary events of the FT and safety barriers of the ET. The ET of the bow-tie model starts from the top event provided by the FT and proceeds toward each branch to calculate the occurrence probability of each consequence based on the failure or success of various safety barriers.</p>	<p>Typically used to analyze accidents, e.g. used in chemical safety and mining through to the rail industry and Aviation sector- i.e. high risk sectors (oil and gas)</p> <p>Can also be applied qualitatively to establish the logical relationship among the components of an accident scenario.</p>	Deals with a hazardous situation and loss of control and can cover multiple risks	<p>Static structure limiting its application in real time monitoring. However can be used in dynamic situations in which the occurrence probability of accident consequences changes.</p> <p>Only represents causes - barriers - events - barriers - consequences relationships for single events or those that can be depicted as cascading trees. More complex interactions are difficult to represent.</p> <p>Not appropriate for cross-sectoral interconnections.</p>	<p>Probabilities of causes and consequences of events are needed for quantitative analyses.</p> <p>No guidance on how to apply the methodology in participatory settings.</p>	Can be applied qualitatively in workshop settings (i.e. 3 hours)	<p>Dynamic risk analysis using bow-tie approach (sciencedirectasets.com)</p>

Tool/approach	Description including phases of use	Application e.g. hazards	Advantages	Disadvantages	Limitations/ Learning Curve	Time taken	More information
Kumu	<p>A flexible, digital visualization tool for mapping systems, stakeholders, community assets, concepts and network analysis</p> <p>It involves creating and importing own datasets and can collaboratively contribute to them to create said maps</p>	<p>Creation of stakeholder maps, systems maps, causal loop diagrams, community asset maps, concept maps, Lombardi diagrams</p>	<p>Could be used by multiple collaborators to map systems of interest.</p> <p>Produces figures that ease understanding of complex relationships</p> <p>Can be integrated to google docs with an extension</p>	<p>License required to keep project's private.</p>	<p>Could be useful for people who are not familiar with digital systems mapping to visualize the connections present in the system they want to explore.</p> <p>Requires some time to get used to and would need a working understanding of network analysis if more in depth assessment is wanted.</p> <p>No clear (stepwise) methodology in how to apply the tool.</p>	<p>3 hours (workshop)</p>	<p>Kumu</p>

Tool/approach	Description including phases of use	Application e.g. hazards	Advantages	Disadvantages	Limitations/ Learning Curve	Time taken	More information
Group model building (original approach)	<p>A participatory method that is used to collaboratively generate integrated systems dynamics models (causal loop diagrams) with stakeholders for the purposes of decision-making. Typically applied in combination with System Dynamics simulations, it refers to a structured approach for client involvement in developing the systems dynamics model, including construction and analysis.</p> <p>The process sees a group of 6 to 15 people guided by 2 moderators , arranged in a semi-circle in front of a whiteboard and/or a projector screen. The set up should be aided by system dynamics modeling software with a graphic interface (e.g. Vensim), which also serves as collective memory (Rouwette and Vennix, 2009).</p>	Organizational change, resource efficiency	<p>Detailed methodology provided on 'client' meetings organization, project specific</p> <p>Ability to analyze complex integrated systems.</p>	<p>When used for quantitative system dynamics assessments, involves prior elaboration on systems parameters (mathematical equations) so that 'clients' will not lose interest during the meeting.</p> <p>Focusses on the development of feedback loops, which may not always suit all problems.</p>	<p>Quite an extensive process that entails:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. identification of the strategic issue to be discussed; 2. elicit relevant variables with which the model construction process can be started; 3. write mathematical equations corresponding to the model parameters (for the in person consultation only crucial formulation and parameter estimation is done); 3. building of a simple running model; 4. further development and testing; 5. elaborate on policy implication of identified conceptualisation; 6. policy elaboration (Rouwette and Vennix, 2009) <p>Need to learn to use Vensim software</p>	Multiple days, particularly in relation to model construction and analysis	Group Model Building

Tool/approach	Description including phases of use	Application e.g. hazards	Advantages	Disadvantages	Limitations/ Learning Curve	Time taken	More information
Group model building (causal loop diagrams)	Simplified GMB process whereby the aim is to develop an conceptual integrated system model together with stakeholders. So not explicitly linked to a systems dynamics model. Aims to improve collective understanding of problems by aligning perceptions (problem framing), elucidating variables, and developing system dynamic management through CLDs (Purwanto et al. 2019)	Environmental management, Water, energy and food	Qualitative approach that can be used to develop coherent policies without quantitative modeling. Cross sectoral applications Ability to analyze complex integrated systems.	Focusses on the development of feedback loops, which may not always suit all problems.	Requires 4 roles that have specific tasks during the workshop: modeler, facilitator, gatekeeper and recorder. Participants conceptualize the problem, identify variables, create individual CLD for each sector, sector models are combined across participants creating a sub-system model, the three sub-system models are integrated in a system model and adjusted for ease of understanding, short evaluative interviews are conducted at the end to evaluate the knowledge of participants (Purwanto et al. 2019)	Prep time 1 month Workshop 4h + 1h for preparation and evaluation	WEF Indonesia application with detailed workshop structure
Causal chains	Process whereby sequential causal relationships are established between one event, process, state, or object (a cause), which then contribute to the production of another event, process, state, or object (an effect) where the cause is partly responsible for the effect, and the effect is partly dependent on the cause.	Widespread application across many domains	Can be adapted to suit different levels of complexity: from a simple linear chain focussed on a single system component to more complex loops, matrices, networks or maps, as with causal loop diagrams (refer Group Model Building)	Simple linear chains do not easily or completely reflect integrated and interconnected systems.	Low (simple linear chains)	3 hours (workshop)	Visualization of causation in social-ecological systems

Tool/approach	Description including phases of use	Application e.g. hazards	Advantages	Disadvantages	Limitations/ Learning Curve	Time taken	More information
Q methodology	Q methodology to study significantly different viewpoints within a given population about a particular topic. Geared towards correlating patterns of thought of the respondents and respondents are the variables. 1) Statements obtained from initial exploratory interviews, 2) the statements are rephrased and clearly articulated, 3) survey distributed online to stakeholders, 4) respondents rank order statements on scale from 'does not reflect my opinion' in a normal distribution.	Used to study different viewpoints within a given population. Number of Q methodologies is still scarce. Q methodology is geared towards correlating patterns of thought of the respondents and the respondents are the variables. By means of factor analyses- end up with clusters which reflect majority and minority viewpoints. Useful for understanding climate adaptation implementation in policy.	Provides insight into different viewpoints and how they differ on different issues, (as opposed to interviews and surveys).	Descriptive instead of visual.	Understands viewpoints, but not a direct mapping of system components and interactions.	Several days (have to obtain statements first through interview)	Governance of climate adaptation, which mode? An exploration of stakeholder viewpoints on how to organize adaptation (springer.com)

Tool/approach	Description including phases of use	Application e.g. hazards	Advantages	Disadvantages	Limitations/ Learning Curve	Time taken	More information
Strategic options and development analysis (SODA)	<p>Based on cognitive or causal mapping, which allows for views to be captured and be structured in a "means-end" format. The unfolding map enables exploration of the situation. It highlights options, causes and constraints. It can uncover self-sustaining cycles and suggest dynamic behavior.</p> <p>Maps in essence are networks (directed graphs) comprising nodes (constructs/statements) and links (causal arrows).</p> <p>Causal maps are those that are produced either from the amalgamation of cognitive maps, or from using the Oval Mapping Technique or mapping live using Decision Explorer</p>	Taking elements of clinical psychology and integrating them in decision-making in organizations public and private, large and small, at senior and middle management levels	Exploration through the causal map leads to a higher probability of more creative solutions and promotes solutions that are more likely to be implemented because the problem construction process is wider and more likely to include richer social dimensions about the blockages to action and organizational change	<p>Participants may be overwhelmed by the use of 'cognitive' so it is recommended to present it to them as causal mapping.</p> <p>Suggests the using of a software tool to visualize the outcome of participant's engagement</p> <p>Authors emphasis the subjectivity nature of this method</p>	<p>SODA comprises paying attention to both Process (namely considering power, politics, personalities, and people – the skills traditionally encompassed by Organizational Development facilitators) and Content (traditionally Operational Research skills of capturing, structuring and analyzing problem statements).</p> <p>Represents, statements that are made as a way of representing a person's 'making sense' of the situation/ problem they believe is faced by the group and how they conceptualize a solution</p>	3 hours (workshop)	described in Ackermann & Eden, 2020

Tool/approach	Description including phases of use	Application e.g. hazards	Advantages	Disadvantages	Limitations/ Learning Curve	Time taken	More information
Soft System Methodology (SSM)	<p>SSM serves as a tool for knowledge elicitation in such circumstances as it aims at understanding the context in which the whole system functions</p> <p>7 steps:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. identify the problem situation in its unstructured form 2. express the problem situation as a rich picture 3. establish root definitions of relevant, purposeful activity systems 4. create conceptual models of the systems named in the root definition 5. compare the systems thinking approach established in the previous set with the real world 6. identify feasible and desirable goals 7. action to improve the problem situation <p>* this sequence is not imposed upon the practitioner, a study can commence at any stage, with iteration and backtracking as essential components</p>	Reviewing working practices in building, construction or engineering industries	Stimulates debate and captures the vision for the future of participants SSM allows the exploitation of individual and socially constructed group knowledge and experience	Organization orientated The way it is presented by the authors requires multiple steps, not achievable in one workshop, as time is dedicated to elaborating on step 2 and 3	Soft Systems Methodology (SSM) may be used to analyze any problem or situation, but it is most appropriate where the problem “cannot be formulated as a search for an efficient means of achieving a defined end; a problem in which ends, goals, purposes are themselves problematic” The objective is to learn about the structures, processes, perceptions and beliefs associated with the case study situation.	3 hours (workshop)	5 cases in Magsood et al. 2001

Tool/approach	Description including phases of use	Application e.g. hazards	Advantages	Disadvantages	Limitations/ Learning Curve	Time taken	More information
Strategic choice approach (SCA)	<p>A balanced collection of tools and concepts developed by management scientists to facilitate communication about the structuring of perplexing decision problems, and also about strategies for making progress toward timely commitments to agreed actions.</p> <p>The principal output of work in the shaping mode takes the form of a decision graph, in which significant connections between pairs of decision areas have been identified in the form of decision links.</p> <p>SCA therefore emphasizes the following:</p> <p>Focus: more emphasis on facilitating decisions than exploring systems; Knowledge: more emphasis on managing uncertainty than processing information; Time: more emphasis on sustaining progress than projecting futures; Skill: more emphasis on structuring communication than reinforcing expertise; Influence: more emphasis on guiding collaboration than exercising control.</p>	<p>In many instances, these tools are employed by project managers, consultants or programme coordinators with responsibility for facilitating decision processes in fields as diverse as environmental conservation, information technology strategy, urban development, product marketing, and health and welfare policy.</p>	<p>Can be achieved during a workshop setting.</p> <p>The author mentions a flip chart as being useful, no systems modeling software required.</p>	<p>Participants may find the comparison stage daunting</p> <p>No development of a systems model</p>	<p>The fundamental concept that is used to guide the work of the shaping mode is that of the decision area. A group of decision makers may agree to express any area of choice that they see ahead of them as a decision area if they can visualize at least two distinct options, and if they expect to have some level of influence in choosing between them</p>	Multiple workshops	Friend 2011

Tool/approach	Description including phases of use	Application e.g. hazards	Advantages	Disadvantages	Limitations/ Learning Curve	Time taken	More information
Strategic Assumption Surfacing and Testing (SAST)	<p>SAST is designed to be used in situations where problems are highly interrelated and often conceal deep divisions between those addressing the problems</p> <p>This methodology can be regarded as having four major stages: (a) group formation, (b) assumption surfacing, (c) dialectical debate, and (d) synthesis.</p>	Coordinating organizations	Could be combined with SSM Dialectic approaches can be more useful than more dialogic and expert-led forms of inquiry	<p>Strategy orientated - does not involve systems exploration</p> <p>Requires extensive debate</p>	Forming two groups that argue two approaches. The groups are forming their assumptions and are brought back together and each group makes the best possible case for its favoured strategy, while clearly identifying the most significant assumptions it is making.		On Strategic Assumption-Making: A Dialectical Approach to Policy and Planning
Scenario planning (Butler et al, 2016)	<p>Scenario planning is a popular and flexible tool used to inform anticipatory adaptation by providing descriptions rather than forecasts or predictions of plausible futures that reflect different perceptions on development. Scenarios can help to overcome complexity and uncertainty in socio-ecological systems. In multi-stakeholder settings- act as objects to promote social learning and collective action and as reference points for development planning. Help enhance systems understanding. Workshop steps 1) what are the drivers of change for livelihoods? 2) What is the desired future for livelihoods? 3) What are the possible futures for livelihoods? 4) What are the priority no regrets adaptations strategies?</p>	Operationalise adaptive pathways and principles by encouraging systems analysis, engaging multiple stakeholders in a learning process, and back casting to identify strategies required to achieve desired and adaptive development.	Adaptation pathways principles can enable multiple stakeholders to mainstream no regrets responses to future uncertainty, into community development planning. In this way adaptation planning can question and potentially redress potentially mal-adaptive development. Facilitates tailoring to local context. Empowers community for exchange of knowledge and ideas.	<p>Predominance of incremental strategies suggests that workshops did not address root causes of community vulnerability and thus the workshops did not provide sufficient learning spirals for participants to analyze issues and revise strategies.</p> <p>No development of a systems model</p>	Requires a long-time frame to effectively execute. Scenario planning should be seen as the first stage of a long-term capacity building process which must be maintained to enable decision makers to reflect and learn iteratively. Must include ongoing evaluation.	Initially 1 day but much more effective over long time frame	

Tool/approach	Description including phases of use	Application e.g. hazards	Advantages	Disadvantages	Limitations/ Learning Curve	Time taken	More information
Critical Scenario Method (Cairns et al, 2010)	Group exercise that involves both broad and deep research on the issue at hand- making sense of all material in relation to each other. First stage is identification of driving forces as factors- social, technological, economic, political, legal, ecological. Second stage is discussion of the relationships between factors- and developing scenario storylines. The 4 scenario frames are in simplistic terms best/best (A1/B1), best/worst (A1/B2), worst/best (A2/B1) and worst/worst (A2/B2). This method also involves asking (ethical) phronetic questions: Where are we going? Is this development desirable? What, if anything, should we do about it? Who gains and who loses, and by which mechanisms of power?	International Businesses futures. Lack of critical reflection on wider implications of International Business activity, as underpinned by implicit assumption of the 'good' of international business	Critical scenario method can be used as a vehicle of mainstream and alternative discourses. Promotes thinking about power and winner and loser perspectives.	Does not incorporate consideration of full range of affected actors	Good for understanding power relationships but perhaps less useful for understanding system interconnections.	3 hours	doi:10.1016/j.futures.2010.08.016 https://www.sciencedirect.com

Tool/approach	Description including phases of use	Application e.g. hazards	Advantages	Disadvantages	Limitations/ Learning Curve	Time taken	More information
Adaptive wheel capacity (Gupta et al, 2010)	22 Criteria Adaptive capacity wheel can help social actors to assess if institutions stimulate the adaptive capacity of society to respond to climate change; and to focus on whether and how institutions need to be redesigned. 6 elements: 1) variety, 2) learning capacity, 3) room for autonomous change, 4) leadership, 5) Resources, 6) Fair governance.	Applied to assess characteristics of institutions to stimulate the capacity of society to adapt to climate change. Can be applied qualitatively or semi-qualitatively. Both applications have implications for scoring adaptive capacity. E.g. used to assess performance of institutions in municipalities with respect to sharing rainfall and groundwater management between residents and government actors.	Provides a comprehensive idea of the dimensions relevant for assessing the adaptive capacity of society through its institutions. Colors used to represent results. Can be used to generate quantitative results- used to rank which institutions are better or worse for adaptive capacity. Useful for self-reflection of policy makers, and presenting the results in an aggregated way may stimulate cross sectoral learning on how institutions in each sector are built.	The wheel has some paradoxes, for example the link between variety and leadership. Strong leadership may lead to less variety- contradictions in criteria. Also not particularly objective evaluation.	Not applied to hazards directly. More about adaptation and institutional capacity, rather than complete analysis of the system	2 hours	The Adaptive Capacity Wheel: a method to assess the inherent characteristics of institutions to enable the adaptive capacity of society (sciencedirect.com)

Tool/approach	Description including phases of use	Application e.g. hazards	Advantages	Disadvantages	Limitations/ Learning Curve	Time taken	More information
Regional interaction framework (Gill et al, 2021)	Regional interaction frameworks can help in understanding the multi-hazard environment of specific spatial events. Frameworks are constructed from 1) International literature, 2) civil protection-bulletins, 3) field observations, 4) stakeholder interviews, 5) workshop. Workshop involves network linkage diagrams for each identified natural hazard, using this to record triggering relationships believed to be present. Participants then complete a blank hazard interaction matrix. Documents participants' perceptions of relevant hazard interactions.	Determine natural hazard interactions. (Identified 50 possible interactions between 19 hazard types)	<p>Good for demonstrating interactions between hazards and visualizing hazard cascades.</p> <p>Integrates diverse evidence types.</p> <p>Scalable- working from global to local scales with different resolutions of information.</p>	<p>Quite an extensive approach, especially in terms of evidence gathering.</p> <p>Some evidence is perception based, which may question its accuracy.</p> <p>Demonstrates hazard interactions, but not broader system analysis</p>	Relatively low, but no clear methodology on how to conduct workshop	3 hours (workshop only)	NHES - Construction of regional multi-hazard interaction frameworks. with an application to Guatemala (copernicus.org)

Appendix 2: Table of sector stakeholder questions aiming to facilitate investigation of the most relevant drivers of sectoral interdependencies and risk typologies to a sector (D1.3, Table 3)

	Functional	Spatial	Financial	Societal
Spill over	<p><i>How reliant are my services/machinery on specific critical infrastructure?</i></p> <p><i>If a particular piece of this infrastructure stopped functioning, how affected would my system's functionality be?</i></p>	<p><i>How close is my infrastructure to a potential hazard?</i></p> <p><i>How proximate is my infrastructure to other infrastructure that could inflict damage in a hazard event?</i></p> <p><i>What other sectors or stakeholders are likely exposed to the same impacts and therefore might be willing partners to cooperate regarding risk reduction measures?</i></p>	<p><i>How interlinked is my sector with the global financial markets?</i></p> <p><i>Are fixed prices built into my supply chain contracts to buffer cascading impacts of price spikes? (Carter et al, 2021).</i></p> <p><i>How likely are consumers to panic buy products in my sector?</i></p>	<p><i>What potential regions might a failure in my sector reach?</i></p> <p><i>What actors would be particularly affected and in what capacities?</i></p> <p><i>In what ways does my disaster risk planning account for potential spill-over effects?</i></p> <p><i>Is disaster planning adaptable and able to deal with dynamic disasters? i.e., does it use dynamic adaptive pathways?</i></p>
Co-dependent	<p><i>Are my services highly coupled with other systems, whereby they are mutually dependent on each other's functionality?</i></p>	<p><i>Are there proximate system services which are highly inter-dependent with each other, which if fail, could threaten the functioning of the system?</i></p>	<p><i>Are the financial systems of my sector highly coupled with financial wellbeing of another, such that if one experiences financial shock, so would mine?</i></p> <p><i>With which sectors are mine tightly coupled to?</i></p>	<p><i>Are there particular groups that are co-dependent for disaster management?</i></p>
Interacting intersecting	<p><i>Does my sector rely on multiple functions that on failure, intersect to compound the overall impact?</i></p>	<p><i>Are there sectors operating in the same location and what are their interacting aspects?</i></p> <p><i>What is the geographical area that could be affected by an incident and are there cross-border impacts?</i></p>	<p><i>How far does my sector interact and intersect with others financially?</i></p>	<p><i>What adaptive capacity is there at the interaction location?</i></p> <p><i>Do we have contingency plans for long-term compounding disasters?</i></p>
Independent intersecting	<p><i>What sectors do we rely on in terms of their functionality, for ours to also function? (i.e., Do we depend on transport service functionality for our services?)</i></p>	<p><i>What is the geographical area that could be affected by an incident and what independent sectors could be impacted?</i></p>	<p><i>What potential impacts in other sectors, when combined could impact the financial security of our sector?</i></p>	<p><i>What is the adaptive capacity to deal with independent risks coalescing?</i></p> <p><i>Are there contingency plans for the long-term effects of disasters?</i></p>

